

ADOPTION PLANS

Tailored approaches for implementing SuCoLo solutions in twelve European cities

As part of Task 4.3 “Adoption Plans of Follower Cities” of the SuCoLo project, Sustainability InnoCenter (Sweden), together with city representatives and other stakeholders, developed these adoption plans to support cities in implementing sustainable and inclusive urban logistics solutions based on the pilot experiences.

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The document builds on experiences in SuCoLo’s three pilot cities (Salzburg, Leipzig, and Merano), as well as insights gathered during two online workshops on Urban Logistics & Sustainable Consumer Behaviour held on 26 November 2025. It also incorporates input from discussions with representatives from SuCoLo follower city Gävle held between January and April 2026, additional stakeholder meetings, and desktop research.

In addition to general implementation guidance, the document includes tailored recommendations and practical steps for the following cities: Agios Nikolaos (Greece), Bochum (Germany), Braşov (Romania), Cologne (Germany), Gävle (Sweden), Kalmar (Sweden), Leipzig (Germany), Malmö (Sweden), Merano (Italy), Osmangazi (Türkiye), Salzburg (Austria) and Stockholm (Sweden).

About the SuCoLo project

Duration: Jan 2024 - June 2026

Implemented within the Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership

Urban logistics is rapidly becoming one of the biggest challenges for cities aiming to reduce emissions and congestion, and improve quality of life. The SuCoLo project seeks to transform last-mile logistics, particularly in urban outskirts, by combining behavioural change with innovative, inclusive cargo-bike-based delivery systems.

Through co-creation, the project brought together key stakeholders to design effective and widely accepted solutions. These were tested as research pilots in **Salzburg (Austria), Leipzig (Germany), and Merano (Italy)**, generating practical insights.

The Salzburg pilot focused on the digital demand side, testing nudges in a simulated webshop environment. The Leipzig pilot deployed a mobile micro-hub with cargo-bike delivery in a low-density outskirts area. The Merano pilot combined cargo-bike sharing with a local courier service for retailers, with a strong accessibility focus.

Leipzig pilot: mobile micro-hub

Leipzig pilot: cargo-bike delivery

Salzburg pilot: webshop prototype

Presentation of Move2Cargo, the pilot project in Merano, May 2025

Accessibility and inclusion considerations across the SuCoLo project

Accessibility and inclusion were integrated across communication, digital tools, pilot activities, and stakeholder engagement throughout the SuCoLo project. To support inclusive access to information, detailed accessibility descriptions were developed for each pilot site using the IG-VAE accessibility assessment methodology and presented in user-friendly formats, including virtual reality tours, interactive maps with accessibility points of interest, and Accessibility Performance Tools.

Area	What SuCoLo implemented
Inclusive communication	Use of inclusive and easy-to-read language; accessibility notification function on project website
Digital accessibility	WCAG 2.2 accessibility assessment of the SuCoLo website and MOQO app, accessibility-focused cargo-bike logistics, climate partnership model, inclusive community mobility solutions.
Accessible dissemination	Sign-language videos, subtitles, translated one-pagers, synchronised transcripts
Pilot design	Accessibility integrated into pilot planning and co-creation activities
User involvement	Workshops and testing with accessibility experts and users with disabilities
Public space & infrastructure	Focus on barrier-free stations, pick-up points, and neighbourhood accessibility

Salzburg pilot: webshop prototype

Inclusive communication with sign-language interpretation

Accessible e-scooter tested in the Merano pilot

Overview of SuCoLo research pilots

	Salzburg	Leipzig	Merano
Timeline and approach	<p>May-June 2025</p> <p>Digital demand-side nudges</p>	<p>May-November 2025</p> <p>Mobile micro-hub & cargo-bike delivery</p>	<p>May 2025 - June 2026</p> <p>Cargo-bike sharing and local courier service</p> <p>Part of the Move2Cargo campaign</p>
Setting	<p>Simulated webshop, Austrian sample</p>	<p>Outskirt district Lützschena-Stahmeln</p>	<p>Compact historic town</p>
Scale	<p>1,101 webshop participants</p>	<p>289 cargo-bike deliveries; 20 cargo-bike rentals; 1 mobile micro-hub van; 1 shared cargo bike</p>	<p>6 shared cargo-bikes deployed (4 electric cargo bikes, 1 non-electric cargo bike, 1 accessible electric scooter); 120 sharing users; 620 cargo-bike deliveries; 11 involved partner shops</p>
Strongest finding	<p>Sustainability values and nudge acceptance strongly influenced sustainable delivery choices; loyalty points and green-leaf nudges performed best</p>	<p>Mobile micro-hubs are flexible entry points for cargo-bike delivery in urban outskirts</p>	<p>Collaborative municipality-retailer-courier model proved workable and generated strong long-term local interest</p>
Key challenge	<p>Digital nudges alone were insufficient to significantly shift delivery behaviour; urgency nudges reduced sustainable delivery choices</p>	<p>Low delivery density limited economic viability; lack of permanent on-site infrastructure</p>	<p>Pick-up station underused; need for long-term operational and financial sustainability</p>
Accessibility aspects	<p>Inclusive communication, accessible webshop design, and co-creation feedback integrated into pilot development</p>	<p>Accessibility-based simulation model; PEBA accessibility plan; interactive 3D virtual tour</p>	<p>Inclusive shared mobility with accessible e-scooter, adapted sharing services, and accessible digital platform</p>

Findings from workshops and stakeholder meetings

Between November 2025 and April 2026, the SuCoLo team organised workshops and meetings with city representatives, logistics providers, local businesses, researchers, and other stakeholders involved in sustainable urban mobility and last-mile delivery solutions. The discussions highlighted common challenges, key insights, and implementation priorities related to sustainable urban logistics solutions in cities.

Screenshot from the SuCoLo workshop, 26.11.25

Screenshot from the SuCoLo workshop, 26.11.25

Meeting between the SuCoLo team and representatives of the Gävle municipality, 10.04.26

Main challenges for further implementation

- **User acceptance and behaviour change** emerged as key barriers, as residents and businesses are often hesitant to change established delivery habits without clear benefits and convenient alternatives.
- **Financial sustainability** was another major challenge, highlighting the need for long-term business models and shared financing beyond temporary pilot funding.
- **Infrastructure and space availability** were also identified as important constraints, particularly in historical centres and dense urban areas where suitable locations for micro-hubs and delivery infrastructure are limited.
- Successful implementation requires **strong stakeholder coordination** between municipalities, logistics providers, retailers, residents, and other actors through clear governance structures, regular communication, and early collaboration.

Findings from workshops and stakeholder meetings

Key insights for cities

- Successful adoption depends on combining technical, behavioural, organisational, and financial measures
- Implementation is not only a technical process, but also a social and organisational one
- Solutions should be adapted to local conditions rather than copied directly from other cities
- Small-scale pilots are effective for testing new concepts before scaling up
- Continuous stakeholder engagement improves acceptance and cooperation
- Communication and awareness-raising activities are essential for behaviour change
- Long-term financial planning is necessary to ensure sustainability

Priorities for implementation

- Early stakeholder involvement
- Flexible pilot design tailored to local needs
- Strong communication and awareness activities, using success stories
- Clear governance and partnership structures
- Sustainable funding and business models
- Integration of accessibility and inclusiveness principles
- Involvement of residents and local communities in the planning process

Adapt to your context

The matrix below connects common city contexts with the SuCoLo pilot solutions that may provide the most suitable starting point for implementation. It is intended to support early planning by helping cities identify approaches that best match their local conditions and priorities.

City profile	Most relevant SuCoLo pilot	Start here	Watch out for
Compact historic centre, active local retail (e.g. Merano, Braşov, Agios Nikolaos)	Merano	Cargo-bike sharing + local courier service for shops; co-financed deliveries	Vandalism risk; pick-up station location matched to real demand
Mid-size city with low-density outskirts (e.g. Gävle, Kalmar)	Leipzig	Mobile micro-hub aggregating multiple CEPs (courier, express and parcel services); cargo-bike rental at high-traffic nodes	Insufficient delivery volume to present a clear business case; enabling courier rest infrastructure
Larger city with strong digital retail (e.g. Stockholm, Cologne, Bochum)	Salzburg + Leipzig	Demand-side behaviour change techniques at checkout combined with local hub piloting	Avoid urgency nudges; segment by sustainability values
Tourist or seasonal town with constrained centre (e.g. Merano, parts of Malmö)	Merano	Inclusive cargo-bike sharing + delivery; visible public events linked to local festivals	Align communications activities with seasonal peaks
Cities with strong accessibility / inclusion mandate	Merano + Leipzig	Accessibility-first design (WCAG 2.2 platforms, accessible vehicles & stations, 3D virtual tours)	Treat accessibility as design driver, not retrofit

Universal SuCoLo adoption plan for all cities

1

Start with a local diagnosis

Map delivery demand, local shops, residential density, vulnerable user needs, existing bike infrastructure, public-space constraints, parcel flows, and suitable micro-hub locations.

2

Jointly produce solutions with local communities

Engage residents, local businesses, schools, sports associations, disability organisations, and community groups through workshops, surveys, pilot events, and co-creation activities to understand local needs, build trust, and increase acceptance of new logistics solutions.

3

Select a pilot model

Designate one or more SuCoLo approaches to focus on:

- E-commerce behaviour change: green delivery labels, loyalty points, default settings, vouchers.
- Physical logistics: mobile or fixed micro-hub, cargo-bike deliveries, CEP cooperation.
- Shared cargo-bike mobility: communal cargo bikes for families, shop owners, associations, and residents.
- Inclusive pick-up/social hub: parcel collection point combined with community placemaking.

4

Engage operational and institutional stakeholders early on

Involve municipalities, transport providers, logistics providers, CEP companies, cargo-bike operators, housing providers, retailers, and business or tourism organisations early to define responsibilities, operational models, infrastructure needs, and long-term governance structures.

Universal SuCoLo adoption plan for all cities

5

Deploy small pilots before scaling

Begin with one district, one hub, 2–6 cargo bikes, 5–10 shops, and a limited delivery zone to test operability and feasibility.

6

Design for inclusion

Keep car access or exceptions for people who need cars, especially disabled people, elderly residents, and care services. Use easy-to-read communication, accessible apps, clear signage, and barrier-free hub locations.

7

Create a business model

Combine municipal support, retailer contribution, user fees, logistics-provider contributions, and project funding. Avoid relying only on temporary grants.

8

Communicate through visible channels

Use public events, markets, schools, stadiums, shopping streets, social media, local influencers, testimonials, and success stories. “Buy local, deliver local” is a strong common slogan.

9

Measure results and optimise

Track deliveries, bike rentals, user profiles, avoided van trips, customer satisfaction, retailer participation, accessibility feedback, vandalism, operating costs, and user willingness to pay.

Recommended implementation timeline

The roadmap spans 2-5 years, depending on local conditions and available resources. The durations shown for each action represent the estimated time required to complete that phase.

Action 1 (1-3 months)	Discovery & mapping Identify community needs, map stakeholders, review accessibility requirements, and select pilot districts with strong demand and operational feasibility.
Action 2 (1-3 months)	Build partnerships Engage municipalities, logistics providers, retailers, mobility operators, and local organisations to define responsibilities and collaboration models.
Action 3 (1-3 months)	Design the pilot Define service scope, hub locations, operational workflows, pricing structure, communications strategy, and monitoring indicators.
Action 4 (1-3 months)	Launch the pilot Start operations in selected districts with active user onboarding, customer support, monitoring systems, and public engagement campaigns.
Action 5 (1-3 months)	Monitor & optimise Collect operational data, accessibility feedback, customer satisfaction insights, and financial performance indicators to optimise the model.
Action 6 (9+ months)	Scale the service Expand to additional districts, strengthen long-term funding arrangements, institutionalise governance, integrate into city mobility systems, and analyse the results and impacts.

Adoption plans for follower cities

Gävle, Sweden

Population: 104,100 inhabitants

Area: 3,197.9 km² (urban area: 55 km²)

Most relevant SuCoLo pilot: Leipzig (accessibility-focused logistics solutions) and Merano (inclusive community-based mobility and cargo-bike sharing)

Relevant initiatives: Gävle Climate Agreement, Viable Cities, Cycle4Climate project

Main interests within SuCoLo: accessibility, inclusivity, cargo-bike logistics, and climate-oriented urban mobility solutions

Photo: gavle.se

<p>Context</p>	<p>Gävle has strong potential to adapt SuCoLo solutions through its existing climate collaboration structures and mobility initiatives. The city is part of the Gävle Climate Agreement, a cooperation platform bringing together businesses, associations, academia, and public actors around climate-driven development. Gävle is also connected to wider sustainability initiatives such as Viable Cities and Cycle4Climate.</p> <p>The city showed particular interest in the Leipzig and Merano pilots, especially their accessibility and inclusivity components. This creates a strong basis for testing accessible cargo-bike logistics, inclusive mobility services, and community-oriented delivery solutions.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Accessibility-focused cargo-bike logistics + climate partnership model + inclusive community mobility solutions.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Establish a small-scale accessible micro-hub connected to local climate partnerships; test shared cargo bikes for families, local associations, and small businesses; integrate accessibility requirements into digital platforms and physical infrastructure; organise co-creation workshops with residents and disability organisations; connect pilot activities with existing cycling and climate initiatives.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Coordination between multiple ongoing mobility and climate projects.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Use the Gävle Climate Agreement as a coordination platform and establish clear governance structures and responsibilities among participating actors.</p>

Malmö, Sweden

Population: 367,924 inhabitants

Area: 157 km²

Photo: Canva

Most relevant SuCoLo pilot: Leipzig (urban logistics and cargo-bike delivery systems) and Salzburg (behaviour-change measures and sustainable delivery choices)

Relevant initiatives: Climate Contract Malmö, Viable Cities, different sustainable urban mobility and climate-neutral city programmes

Potential applications of SuCoLo solutions: micro-hub logistics, cargo-bike delivery, behaviour-change measures, climate-neutral last-mile logistics, and inclusive urban mobility solutions

Context	The adaptation plan should focus on reducing van traffic in dense neighbourhoods and commercial districts while improving accessibility and convenience for residents and local businesses. Malmö can also build on its existing climate-transition initiatives and collaborative governance structures.
Best-fit approach	Integrated micro-hub network + behaviour-change measures + climate-neutral last-mile logistics.
Actions	Establish a network of fixed or semi-mobile micro-hubs in dense residential and commercial areas; test cargo-bike deliveries for local retailers and groceries; integrate green delivery defaults, loyalty rewards, and sustainable delivery messaging into online checkouts; cooperate with housing companies and mobility providers; include accessibility and inclusive design requirements in all pilot infrastructure and digital platforms.
Key risks	Coordinating complexity between multiple actors.
Risk mitigation activities	Establish a dedicated city-led coordination structure with clear partner roles, shared targets, and continuous stakeholder dialogue; begin with one or two pilot districts before scaling city-wide.

Adoption plans for participating cities

Leipzig, Germany

Population: 633,500 inhabitants

Area: 298 km²

Photo: Canva

Pilot focus: scaling and integrating micro-hub logistics solutions into wider urban and peri-urban districts.

<p>Context</p>	<p>The Leipzig Logistics Living Lab, run by Leipzig University, tested a mobile micro-hub and cargo-bike delivery model in the outer district of Lützschena-Stahmeln between May and November 2025. The pilot demonstrated that mobile micro-hubs can support cargo-bike logistics in lower-density urban areas where permanent infrastructure is not yet available. The pilot included approximately 289 deliveries, a mobile micro-hub van, and cargo-bike rental activities.</p> <p>Workshop discussions highlighted Leipzig as a relevant model for mid-sized cities with lower-density outskirts, ageing populations in some districts, and dual urban and peri-urban logistics needs. The pilot also emphasized the importance of balancing sustainable logistics measures with accessibility needs and confirmed that cargo-bike logistics in lower-density areas require sufficient delivery volumes, stakeholder cooperation, and flexible operational models to become economically sustainable.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Mobile or semi-mobile micro-hub network combined with consolidated cargo-bike delivery services and accessibility-oriented logistics planning.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Expand micro-hub operations to additional districts; test shared logistics models involving multiple CEP providers; strengthen cooperation with local retailers and neighbourhood services; integrate accessible and barrier-free design principles; use visible demonstrations and success stories to support wider adoption.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Low delivery density in peri-urban areas.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Consolidate deliveries from multiple CEP providers and local retailers; connect logistics services with neighbourhood mobility initiatives and public-space functions; gradually scale operations district by district to build stable demand and long-term operational efficiency.</p>

Merano, Italy

Population: 41,000 inhabitants

Area: 26,3 km²

Photo: italia.it

Pilot focus: continuation, scaling up, and regional replication of the SuCoLo pilot model, with a particular focus on cargo bike sharing and delivery services.

<p>Context</p>	<p>Merano is a compact historic town in South Tyrol with a strong local-retail mix and an active tourism economy. The Move to Cargo pilot deployed 4 electric cargo bikes (2 Vario Business, 2 Vario Family), 1 muscle-powered Muli Muskel cargo bike, and 1 accessible electric Sunrise Sterling EcoMover scooter across 6 host stations. The delivery service operated by FIX-Fahrradkurier involved 11 partner shops and reached approximately 620 B2C deliveries by April 2026, while 120 users registered for the sharing services.</p> <p>Workshop discussions and local feedback showed strong interest in continuing and expanding the services beyond the pilot phase. Around 40 local actors expressed concrete interest in future continuation, including associations interested in long-term cargo-bike rental models. The pilot also demonstrated the value of combining sustainable logistics with accessibility and inclusive mobility solutions.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Permanent community-based cargo-bike sharing and local delivery system combined with accessible mobility services and retailer partnerships.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Secure long-term operational funding and co-financing; maintain and expand the existing host-station network; scale cargo-bike sharing and delivery services to additional neighbourhoods and municipalities in South Tyrol; strengthen cooperation with retailers, tourism actors, and associations; continue accessibility-oriented activities and inclusive mobility solutions; replicate the model across the Province of Bolzano using the SuCoLo pilot experience as a regional reference case.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Long-term operational and financial sustainability after the project.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Develop mixed financing models combining municipal support, retailer contributions, user fees, regional funding, and long-term partnership agreements with local businesses and associations.</p>

Salzburg, Austria

Population: 157,000 inhabitants

Area: 66 km²

Photo: Canva

Pilot focus: Testing digital behaviour change techniques in a simulated webshop to encourage local cargo bike delivery

<p>Context</p>	<p>Salzburg is a historic small city in western Austria. Known as a major tourist destination and cultural center, it also serves as a regional transport node. The Salzburg pilot developed a webshop simulator that tested the effect of different behaviour change techniques (BCTs) on users' sustainable delivery choices. The results showed that one's sustainability values and general acceptance of nudges strongly influenced delivery decisions, while certain messages such as loyalty points and green-leaf labels performed better than urgency-based approaches. Stakeholder discussions and feedback highlighted Salzburg as a relevant reference case for cities with strong digital retail activity and interest in influencing digital consumer behaviour.</p> <p>Salzburg is currently developing its future Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan 2040 (SUMP) with an accompanying Sustainable Urban Logistics Plan (SULP), as well as rolling out its bikesharing programme S-Bike. Therefore, knowledge transfer from the other pilots in Leipzig and Merano (particularly citizen bikesharing) carry greater relevance in the immediate term.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>In the immediate term, permanent community-based e-bike-sharing, with a long-term vision towards incorporating cargo-bikes, accessible motorised scooters, digital nudging elements, and logistics solutions.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Rolling-out of bikesharing in sequential phases; the first of which in the most critical locations, followed by in neighbouring villages in the province of Salzburg and deepening peri-urban and rural systems. Optimising the mix of bicycle types (i.e., e-bikes, e-cargo bikes and e-bikes with children seat).</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Lagging uptake of bikesharing due to low user awareness, and in peri-urban and rural areas due to low population density.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Initial roll-out in high-demand central locations to build visibility and user confidence before expanding to surrounding villages and rural areas. Optimise the vehicle mix to meet diverse user needs, and integrate the S-Bike programme with existing public transport connections in a Mobility-as-a-Service platform to encourage multimodal use.</p>

Adoption plans for other European cities

Agios Nikolaos, Crete, Greece

Population: 27,800 inhabitants (summer: up to 80,000)

Area: 511.7 km²

Closest SuCoLo pilot: Merano (compact tourism town with active local retail)

Photo: expedia.co.uk

<p>Context</p>	<p>Agios Nikolaos is a coastal tourism town on the Gulf of Mirabello with a strong seasonal demand pattern, six- to ten-fold increase in population between winter and summer. Year-round demand is small, retail is concentrated in the historic core around Lake Voulismeni, and the regional unit covers a large rural area with five small islands. The municipality already has experience with EU climate frameworks through the Covenant of Mayors and an existing SEAP, which gives a governance entry point for SuCoLo activities.</p> <p>The biggest logistics challenge is the seasonality gap: any service that needs year-round volume will struggle. The opportunity is precisely that flexible, low-fixed-cost models (cargo-bike sharing, light delivery to historic-core retailers) can absorb the summer peak without investing in infrastructure that sits idle in winter.</p> <p>Agios Nikolaos should adapt SuCoLo for a coastal, tourism-heavy context. The strongest entry point is reducing van traffic in central/tourist areas while supporting hotels, shops, restaurants, and residents.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Tourism-oriented cargo-bike delivery + seasonal micro-hub + hotel/retail partnerships</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Create a summer-season micro-hub near the centre or port; offer cargo-bike delivery for shops, hotels and restaurants; test luggage/light-goods delivery; use clear tourist-facing communication; include e-cargo bikes suitable for slopes and heat.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Seasonality.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Operate a high-intensity summer pilot, then shift bikes to schools, municipal services or local businesses in the off-season.</p>

Bochum, Germany

Population: 375,600 inhabitants

Area: 145.7 km²

Closest SuCoLo pilot: combination of Salzburg (behavioural change techniques) and Leipzig (mobile micro-hubs).

Photo: bochum-tourismus.de

<p>Context</p>	<p>Bochum has experience with local fulfilment logistics, EV-based delivery, cargo bikes, and same-day retail delivery services. The city is also involved in the PROMISE project (DUT) and has tested innovative logistics solutions such as an autonomous last-mile delivery pilot together with REWE supermarket and Volkswagen. Bochum's experience also demonstrates the importance of combining technical logistics solutions with strong public communication and citizen engagement through visible local events and partnerships.</p> <p>In Bochum, the key question is therefore not how to start sustainable urban logistics initiatives, but how SuCoLo solutions can strengthen and expand existing activities, particularly through behavioural change techniques, accessibility-focused approaches, and citizen-oriented communication and engagement strategies.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>"Buy local, deliver local" fulfilment model combined with EV/cargo-bike hybrid logistics and behaviour-change communication measures.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Build on existing local logistics initiatives and pilot cargo-bike delivery for local retailers and groceries; integrate green delivery messaging and customer incentives into local shopping platforms; use public events, shopping districts, and sports venues for awareness campaigns; test micro-hubs connected to fulfilment and EV delivery systems; include accessibility and inclusive design elements in pilot activities.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Low citizen engagement and limited visibility of sustainable logistics solutions.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Use highly visible public communication channels, neighbourhood ambassadors, local events, and partnerships with retailers, sports organisations, and community actors to increase awareness and participation.</p>

Braşov, Romania

Population: 237,600 inhabitants

Area: 267.32 km²

Photo: romaniatourism.com

Closest SuCoLo pilot: Leipzig (micro-hubs and cargo-bike logistics) and Merano (historic urban environment and tourism-oriented mobility)

<p>Context</p>	<p>Braşov is a historic Transylvanian city with a strong tourism profile and a compact, walkable historic centre surrounded by mountain landscapes. The city's dense Old Town, active retail and hospitality sector, and high visitor flows create favourable conditions for sustainable last-mile logistics and cargo-bike delivery solutions. At the same time, mountain topography and winter conditions may make some logistics operations more seasonal.</p> <p>Braşov is already operating a cargo-bike micro-hub in the city centre as part of another DUT project, PROMISE. The city therefore has strong potential to expand cargo-bike logistics through gradual scaling of the existing micro-hub model, stronger cooperation with local businesses, and broader integration of sustainable delivery services into the historic city centre and tourism-related activities.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>City-centre micro-hub combined with cargo-bike logistics for residents, small businesses, retail, and tourism-related deliveries.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Expand the existing micro-hub capacity to 5-6 cargo bikes; strengthen cooperation with local retailers, cafés, hotels, and tourism businesses; introduce shared booking and delivery support for residents and small businesses; test seasonal delivery services adapted to tourism peaks; collect user feedback and success stories to support future scaling and partnerships with larger logistics operators.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>High demand may exceed the current hub and vehicle capacity, especially during tourism seasons.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Scale gradually through additional cargo bikes, temporary seasonal hubs, flexible delivery schedules, and stronger cooperation with local businesses and municipal partners.</p>

Cologne, Germany

Population: 1.1 million inhabitants

Area: 405.15 km²

Photo: Canva

Closest SuCoLo pilot: a hybrid model combining Salzburg's use of BCTs for digital retail deliveries with Leipzig's micro-hub approach in lower-density outer districts.

<p>Context</p>	<p>Cologne is the fourth-largest city in Germany, a major commercial hub on the Rhine, with a dense historic centre around the Cathedral and a wide ring of mixed-density outer districts such as Mülheim, Porz, Ehrenfeld, and Chorweiler. E-commerce activity is high, making Cologne one of Germany's major CEP markets, while last-mile deliveries are still largely dominated by van-based fleets struggling with congestion in the city centre.</p> <p>For a city of Cologne's size, two SuCoLo approaches are particularly relevant: demand-side behavioural change techniques in online retail and micro-hub-based cargo-bike logistics in lower-density districts. While the historic centre already hosts several private cargo-bike delivery services, outer residential areas could benefit from Leipzig-inspired mobile or semi-mobile micro-hubs and consolidated last-mile logistics solutions.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Fixed or semi-mobile micro-hubs combined with behavioural nudges and retailer-supported cargo-bike deliveries.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Pilot one consolidation point near a dense shopping or residential district; test cargo-bike deliveries from local retailers and parcel operators; introduce green delivery labels, loyalty rewards, or default sustainable delivery options in participating online shops; run communication campaigns promoting cleaner and more accessible shopping streets.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Competing street-space demands and resistance to reallocating public space.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Use modular and temporary hub infrastructure, flexible loading windows, and clear exemptions for disabled users, care services, and essential vehicle access.</p>

Kalmar, Sweden

Population: 73,300 inhabitants

Area: 956.1 km²

Photo: kalmar.com

Closest SuCoLo pilot: Leipzig (mid-size city with low-density outskirts and an ageing population in some districts)

<p>Context</p>	<p>Kalmar is a coastal university town on Sweden's southeastern Baltic coast, with a compact historic centre around Kalmar Castle and the cathedral, a clear ring of lower-density residential districts, and a strong tertiary-education sector through Linnaeus University. The municipality also includes rural and island areas connected through the Öland Bridge, creating a typical Nordic mix of urban and peri-urban logistics needs.</p> <p>Sweden's Klimatkontrakt framework, coordinated through the Viable Cities programme, provides a natural strategic framework for SuCoLo-related activities in Kalmar, similarly to Gävle and Malmö. Kalmar's combination of moderate urban scale, lower-density outer districts, ageing population groups in some areas, and strong cycling culture makes the Leipzig pilot particularly relevant as a reference model.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Shared cargo-bike mobility combined with neighbourhood logistics hubs and local delivery services for residents, families, and small retailers.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Establish small-scale neighbourhood cargo-bike hubs connected to residential districts, schools, and community facilities; test shared cargo bikes for families, elderly residents, and local associations; support local retailer delivery services using cargo bikes; integrate accessibility and inclusive design into digital and physical infrastructure; connect pilot activities with existing cycling and climate-neutral city initiatives.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Low delivery density and seasonal fluctuations in usage across peri-urban and residential areas.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Combine logistics services with everyday community uses such as school trips, family transport, sports associations, local events, and neighbourhood services to ensure regular year-round use and broader public engagement.</p>

Osmangazi (Türkiye)

Population: 885,000 inhabitants

Area: 621 km²

Photo: Wikipedia

Closest SuCoLo pilot: Merano (compact historic centre with active local retail), adapted for UNESCO-heritage sensitivity and local urban logistics challenges

<p>Context</p>	<p>Osmangazi district municipality forms the historic core of Bursa in the Marmara Region of Türkiye. Osmangazi combines dense commercial areas, traditional markets, residential neighbourhoods, and UNESCO World Heritage sites, creating complex urban logistics conditions in a heritage-sensitive environment.</p> <p>Workshop discussions highlighted challenges related to vandalism, limited stakeholder interest, and regulatory complexity, particularly for cargo-bike infrastructure and shared mobility systems in protected historic areas. At the same time, Osmangazi is already involved in the DUT project, PROMISE, exploring micro-hubs, sustainable logistics, and innovative delivery solutions. This creates opportunities to test carefully controlled, heritage-compatible, and community-oriented sustainable urban logistics models.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>A heritage-sensitive and community-oriented urban logistics living lab focused on small-scale, supervised micro-hubs and low-emission last-mile delivery solutions. The model should combine sustainable urban logistics with heritage preservation through stakeholder co-creation, temporary modular infrastructure, and carefully regulated cargo-bike operations adapted to dense historic environments.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Establish a pilot micro-hub in one historic district; test supervised cargo-bike deliveries for local retailers and municipal services; involve shopkeepers, residents, and heritage authorities in co-creation activities; and explore modular, temporary, and heritage-compatible logistics infrastructure.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Vandalism, limited stakeholder engagement, and restrictions related to UNESCO heritage protection.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Use supervised or staffed hubs, secure storage and monitoring systems, strong municipal coordination, and early cooperation with heritage authorities, local businesses, and community actors.</p>

Stockholm, Sweden

Population: 960,000 inhabitants

Area: 187 km²

Photo: Canva

Closest SuCoLo pilot: Hybrid approach combining two pilots - Salzburg (BCTs in digital retail) and Leipzig (micro-hub consolidation in lower-density outer districts)

<p>Context</p>	<p>Stockholm is the capital of Sweden and the largest urban region in the Nordic countries, spread across 14 islands and surrounded by multiple municipalities within Stockholm County. The city has set an ambitious climate-neutrality target for 2030 and is already implementing a broad range of sustainable urban mobility and logistics initiatives. Cycling infrastructure is well developed in central districts, although accessibility and logistics conditions vary across lower-density outer areas.</p> <p>Stockholm already has ongoing cargo-logistics initiatives. The role of SuCoLo in Stockholm is therefore not to duplicate existing activities, but to complement them with additional behavioural change approaches, accessibility-oriented methodologies, and lessons from lower-density logistics pilots. In particular, Salzburg's BCTs, Leipzig's experience with consolidation and micro-hubs in outer districts, and the accessibility approaches tested within the SuCoLo project may provide valuable additions to Stockholm's existing mobility and logistics ecosystem.</p>
<p>Best-fit approach</p>	<p>Integration of behavioural change techniques, accessibility-oriented logistics planning, and micro-hub consolidation into existing sustainable urban logistics initiatives.</p>
<p>Actions</p>	<p>Test BCTs in online retail and delivery platforms; strengthen cargo-bike logistics and micro-hubs in lower-density districts; integrate accessibility and inclusive design into logistics services; cooperate with micromobility and logistics operators; and use public campaigns and incentives to support sustainable delivery behaviour.</p>
<p>Key risks</p>	<p>Fragmentation between multiple ongoing mobility, logistics, and climate initiatives.</p>
<p>Risk mitigation activities</p>	<p>Use existing climate-neutral city frameworks and cross-sector partnerships to coordinate logistics, mobility, accessibility, and behavioural-change activities under a shared long-term strategy.</p>

Additional resources

This document serves as an entry point to a broader set of SuCoLo deliverables. Follower and interested cities are encouraged to use them together.

Reports on the research pilots' design, implementation, and results

SuCoLo Toolkit

Recommendations for Sustainable Urban Bicycle Logistics Policies

<https://zenodo.org/records/19471653>

<https://sucolo.eu/toolkit/>

<https://sucolo.eu/toolkit/recommendation-for-sustainable-urban-bicycle-logistic-policies/>

Authors:

Svitlana Baliuk, Harris Stamatopoulos (Sustainability InnoCenter)
Michael Thelen (Salzburg Research)

The content of this material does not necessarily represent the official position of the European Union, the DUT Partnership, or the participating funding agencies.

Get in touch

SuCoLo Project Coordinator: Michael Thelen, Salzburg Research

✉ michael.thelen@salzburgresearch.at

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🌐 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sucolo>